

Household Clothing Sample Collection CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
3	Visit	Baseline Visit Follow-up Visit 1 Follow-up Visit 2 Follow-up Visit 3
4	Participant ID	
5	Sample ID	
6	Sample Type?	Chitenji Other (specify) (go to Q7)
6b	When was the Chitenji last worn?	Day before sample collection Day of sample collection
<p><i>You have completed data collection for this sample.</i></p> <p><i>Please thank them for their time.</i></p>		
7	Staff signature	
8	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY